

**REFERENTIAL FOCUS OF SENTENCES WITH AUTHORIZATION AND DEAUTHORIZATION
STRUCTURES IN ENGLISH MEDIA TEXT**

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ABSTRACT

The paper is devoted to the study of the types of referential focus in sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures in the English media text. The paper shows the dependence of objective reporting or interpretative comment on referential features of subject sources of information, direct or reported speech and usage of evaluation vocabulary. The paper also explains that the statements with the shifted referential focus can introduce evaluative or interpretive components into reporting, and the sentences with concentrated referential focus guarantee objective coverage of events with reliable and identifiable sources of information. On the basis of quantitative analysis referential types of subject sources are summed up and the dominant referential focus sentence type is defined.

Keywords: referential subject; non-referential subject; authorization structures; deauthorization structures; concentrated, diffusive, shifted referential focus; subject referential density.

Introduction. One of the generally accepted criteria for the quality of media information today is the accuracy and identifiability of its sources. The problem of reliable media sources involves a detailed study of the subjects of reference acting as information sources. If we proceed from the reference theory which has developed in linguistic semantics [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], then we are talking about the ontological parameter of reference of subjects which act as sources of information. In the existing linguistic tradition, subjects which act as information sources are components of the media text reference base, relevant for the text production, and are its obligatory actants. In studies on reference, the terminological apparatus of logical semantics is used, where an event is described as a predicate, and its arguments (participants) as actants (obligatory participants) and circumstants (optional participants) [1]. In our description, subjects which act as sources of information in authorization and deauthorization structures are obligatory components of the reference base and are necessary to ensure the functional and semantic completeness of any media text. In any media text, the conventional scheme for presenting material presupposes the presence of the obligatory component in the form of information sources with their quoted speech, shared opinion or open evaluation. These subjects can

be a) definite, or referential, i.e. identifiable by the reader and thus referring to the particular person or people in the real world, used in authorization structures; b) indefinite, or non-referential, i.e. unidentifiable by the reader and thus non-referring to a real person or group of people because of the vague nomination or implication, used in deauthorization structures.

The purpose of work is to define correlations between objective reporting and interpretative comment depending on the types of referential focus of sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures in the English media text. **The object of the study** in this paper is sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures from the news article in the online edition of The Guardian dated January 9, 2024 “Gabriel Attal becomes youngest French PM as Macron tries to revive popularity”.

Analysis and discussion. Using the continuous sampling method, the sentences containing authorization and deauthorization structures have been selected. These selected sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures have subjects (sources of information) either verbally expressed or implied. The total number of selected structures is 20 and they are presented in the table below according to the referential characteristics.

Table 1.

Sentences containing authorization and deauthorization structures with referential and non-referential subjects acting as information sources

Sentences with	
Referential subjects in authorization structures	Non-referential subjects in deauthorization structures
1) Attal described his appointment as a bold move by Macron. 2) "I want to see it as a symbol of audacity," he said . 3) Attal , who will appoint a new government in the coming days, said he would pursue what he described as Macron's pro-business drive to transform the French economy. 4) "I'm well aware of the context in which I take on this job," he said . 5) He said he was thinking of workers "who get up every morning to go to work ... and sometimes can't make ends meet". 6) Jordan Bardella , the 28-year-old president of RN, said Macron was just trying to attach himself to Attal's popularity. 7) "By appointing Gabriel Attal ... Emmanuel Macron wants to cling to his popularity in opinion polls..." he said . 8) Macron wrote on X that he was counting on Attal's energy and engagement to restore the spirit of 2017. 9) Macron said in his new year address that, alongside his long-stated goal of bringing France back to full employment, he wanted what he called a "civic re-armament". 10) Sylvain Maillard, head of Macron's Renaissance party in parliament, said Attal could be relied on to "faithfully" carry Macron's project for the country. 11) "What can the French expect from this fourth prime minister and fifth government in seven years?" said Le Pen .	1) Attal, 34, who was serving as education minister, has been referred to as a "baby Macron"... 2) He is considered to be the best-known and most recognisable face of the close circle of young politicians around the president. 3) A source at the Elysée described Attal as a symbol of the young "Macron generation" and said his appointment was about returning to the fundamentals of the president's centrist politics. 4) But the source also said that making Attal prime minister was about "the fight against populism, which is quite strong in France ahead of the European elections" in June. 5) Jordan Bardella is known for his heated TV debates with Attal. 6) Attal, who has also served as budget minister, became a household name as government spokesperson during the Covid pandemic and is regarded by some as a master of political communication. 7) A calm, careful speaker who can sometimes be ferocious in political TV debates against the far right, he is known to believe that it is important "to speak to people's hearts". 8) Macron's decision to replace the former prime minister Élisabeth Borne and reshuffle the government is not regarded as a fundamental political shift. 9) The president is trying to move beyond a difficult past year that divided his party and was seen by some as an ideological victory for the ideas of Le Pen and the radicalised right.

The table shows that in most cases one sentence contains one subject which is the source of information, and the subjects have different referential characteristics. Let us present the results of the referential and non-referential subjects in proportion as they are incorporated in the news article.

Diagram 1. Representation of the subject's referential types in the authorization and deauthorization structures in the English media text

In the analyzed text, referentially specific subjects have a bigger representation accounting for 55% of all identified sources of information, whereas the share of non-referential indefinite subjects is 45%. The subject-

referential density of the news text is defined by the amount of subjects which act as sources of information. The news article under consideration is full of such references: they are presented in almost every sentence,

which gives grounds to qualify this article as having a high degree of subject-referential density.

Identification of referential types of subjects is directly related to the referential focus of the sentences with the authorization and deauthorization structures. To determine their referential focus, the composition and configuration of the information sources were analyzed. The concept of referential focus was proposed by A.A. Negryshev [2], by which the researcher understands the density of linking textual information to the reported fragment of reality. In discourse the referential focus is the degree of reporting clarity and precision of a real event in the news text. Referential focus also characterizes the degree of factuality vs. evaluation in the text, i.e. its correspondence or deviation from the strategy of precise reflection of reality towards interpretation and comment [2]. The referential focus of the statement is determined, among other things, by the composition and configuration of the subjects which are information sources. So, according to the concept of A.A. Negryshev, if an event is conveyed in a text only by obligatory components and those optional actants that do not take the message out of the sphere of factography into the field of evaluative interpretations, then such a text has a *concentrated* referential focus. If the actant composition of the text changes by eliminating obligatory actants and/or due to the inclusion of optional actants and related events, then this type of referential focus can be called *diffusive*. With such a focus, the reference base of the text either expands or narrows, which leads to weakening of the density of the factual connection of the text to the reality. In the case of a *shifted* referential focus, factography practically is replaced by interpretation, which can be achieved both by expanding the reference base and by using logical and stylistic evaluation techniques that appear at different levels of the text structure [1].

Using this distinction in the type of referential focus as the basis for analyzing the selected sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures, we will try to present our observations taking into account the referential variety of the subject sources from the table above.

Let us start with the sentences that have the following type of the reference base: “subject” + “content of the statement” as a verbal action of the subject, and the verbal action of the subject is framed as direct speech without modifications and not taken out of context. In our material, the example of this type of reference base is: “*I’m well aware of the context in which I take on this job,*” **he [Attal] said**. Here *he* (the subject, which is identified by the reader, refers to Attal, and is coded by the personal pronoun) informed the reporters of his awareness regarding his new job (the content of the statement). This type of referent event (event-statement) involves the most accurate reproduction of the content of the statement in the news text because it is quoted. The obligatory subject component introduces the message as factual and accurate as it was said by the subject and not transformed by the journalist, therefore statements of this type have a *concentrated* referential focus. In the selected material there are only four statements of this kind (numbers are 2, 4, 7, 11 in the table

above), thus the total share of statements with a concentrated referential focus in our material is 20%.

If the subjects which act as information sources are referential but on their behalf the data are given in the compressed, interpretative or evaluative form and coded as reported speech, then this type of referential focus of the utterance can be called *diffusive*. The referent base of such a statement reflects the formula “subject” + “compressive, transformed or interpretative content of the statement.” With such a focus, the referent base of the statement is often narrowed, which leads to a weakening of the density of the factual connection of the text to the reality. This same type includes statements in which information is presented on behalf of non-referential generalized subjects (not found in this particular media text). Statements with a diffusive referential focus in our material include examples numbered 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10 in the table above, which make 35% of all the selected sentences. Statements of this type presented on behalf of a specific referential subject in the form of indirect speech have a diffusive referential focus and may contain evaluative vocabulary, for instance: *Attal, who will appoint a new government in the coming days, said he would pursue what he described as Macron’s pro-business drive to transform the French economy*. In this case, the obligatory subject component *Attal* introduces the message in a compressed form, which contains assessment (*pro-business drive*), thus it allows us to classify statements of such kind as belonging to this group with the diffusive referential focus.

In the case of a *shifted* referential focus, factography practically gives way to interpretation, which can be achieved mainly due to the incorporation of evaluative adjectives, adverbs or other lexical units with evaluative components into sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures. Thereby journalists make their presence in the text visible, and in combination with unidentifiable information sources journalists avoid responsibility for what is being reported. In our material these are the sentences with the implied (verbally not expressed) subjects, for example: *Attal has been referred to as a “baby Macron”*; *He is considered to be the best-known and most recognisable face of the close circle of young politicians around the president*; *A source at the Elysée described Attal as a symbol of the young “Macron generation”*; *But the source also said that making Attal prime minister was about “the fight against populism”*; *Jordan Bardella is known for his heated TV debates with Attal*; *Attal became a household name and is regarded by some as a master of political communication*; *A calm, careful speaker who can sometimes be ferocious in political TV debates against the far right, he is known to believe that it is important “to speak to people’s hearts”*; *Macron’s decision is not regarded as a fundamental political shift*. The reference base of such statements can be represented as “subject” + “evaluation of the content of the statement.” In the examples of this group, there are references to an anonymous information source: *a source at the Elysée described, the source said*. The usage of the definite article with the second mentioning doesn’t make the source definite or referential, but it is guided

by the grammar rules. The nominal elements (*a source at the Elysée* and *the source*) show coreferential correlation with the designated object in the real world and from the point of view of structure the independent position of denotative names in a sentence [3]. In all other examples, the subjects are implied and eliminated from the sentence structure: it is not mentioned who *considers, knows* or *regards* something. A specific feature of sentences with the shifted referential focus, represented by implied subjects, is the emphasis on the message conveyed in a compressed (transformed, interpretative or evaluative) form in structures like: *has been referred to, is considered, is known, is regarded by some, is not regarded*. Another peculiarity of such news reports accompanied by the author's assessment is that the topic

of the message is no longer the new event itself, but its comment, i.e. that constitutes not an eventful, but an interpretive field. In other words, in such statements, the source of information is characterized by double subject representation (subject which is the information source + subject which is the text author), which expands the referent base of the message, bringing it into the interpretive sphere. It is noteworthy that this type can include statements with both referential and non-referential subjects. In our material, statements with the shifted referential focus (9 units in total, all with non-referential subjects as in the table above) account for 45% of all the selected units. Let us present the distribution of analyzed statements in Diagram 2, taking into account their referential focus.

Diagram 2. Representation of the statements with different types of referential focus in the English media text

The diagram shows that the statements with the shifted referential focus dominate in the analyzed media text and constitute 45% of all the selected samples, the sentences with the diffusive referential focus have a smaller share equal to 35%, and the sentences with the concentrated referential focus are represented in the least proportion making up 20%. The dominance of the statements with the shifted referential focus is explained by the fact that they allow the journalist to bring the evaluative and interpretive components into the news reporting, which are mixed with the sentences with concentrated referential focus. The latter is necessary even in the minor proportion in order to provide or pretend to provide objective coverage of events and unbiased reporting with reliable and identifiable sources of information.

Conclusion. Thus, three types of referential focus in sentences with authorization and deauthorization structures: concentrated, diffusive, shifted depend on 1) the referential features of the subject source of information, 2) direct or reported speech, and 3) presence or absence of evaluation vocabulary. The configuration of obligatory actants (subjects which act as sources of information) and the nature of the referential focus of the sentence with authorization and deauthorization structures make it possible to state the degree of its compliance or deviation from the objective reporting and interpretative comment. The statements with the shifted referential focus can introduce evaluative or interpretive components into reporting, and the sentences with concentrated referential focus guarantee objective coverage of events with reliable and identifiable sources of

information. These aspects are directly related to linguistic criteria for the reliability of reporting, the systematic development of which seems to be a promising task in modern linguistics.

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